

MECHANISMS OF INOTROPIC EFFECT ON CARDIAC MUSCLE CONTRACTION
ACTIVITY OF CERTAIN DITERPENOID ALKALOIDS

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Annotation: *The article discusses the relationship between the inotropic effects of the alkaloids 15-hydroxyazometine atysine (15-GAA) and acetoxyazometine atysine (15-AAA) isolated from a plant belonging to the genus Aconitum zeravshanicum with their structures, as well as the mechanisms underlying their positive and negative inotropic activity.*

Key words: *Papillary muscle, sarcoplasmic reticulum, frequency of stimulation, rianodine receptors, , Ca²⁺ions, contraction force.*

Introduction. Currently, the urgent task is to look for compounds isolated from the plant, which have potential pharmacological activity, promising for the development of new approaches to the treatment of cardiac arrhythmias all over the world. To date, with the help of these

compounds, important information has been obtained about the cellular and molecular mechanisms of cardiac arrhythmias and the most promising targets for their treatment [1]. In addition, thanks to these compounds, important aspects of the pharmacological regulation of these targets were identified, which

made it possible to develop effective methods for modulating their functional state. In general, valuable information was obtained in the process of studying compounds isolated from the plant, which ensured significant progress in the development and creation of new promising drugs for the treatment of heart rhythm disorders. Because the results obtained when describing the specific aspects of the inotropic mechanism of action of diterpene alkaloids are.

Material and techniques. In experiments, preparations of the papillary muscle of the rat heart were used as objects. White, breedless rats (200-250 g) were immobilized under the influence of diethyl ether, lifeless in the tservical dislocation method and opened the chest in a surgical manner. The heart was separated from the blood vessels and fixed to the container of the drug, in which the saline solution was filled. The Krebs saline solution used was prepared in the following composition (mm): NaCl-118; KCl-4.7; CaCl₂-2.5; MgSO₄-1.2; KH₂PO₄-1.1; glucose-5.5; NaHCO₃-25, pH-7.4. The heart was cut off from the middle part and the papillary muscle located in the right ventricle was separated. The average diameter of the papillary muscle drug is 0.4-0.8 mm, the length is 1-3 mm. ni makes up. The muscle preparation was

fixed to the wall of the experimental chamber (5 ml) using thread rings, and the mechanotron F30 (Hugo SACHE, Germany) hook with the second end. Experiment chamber perfusion at a rate of 6 ml/min with Krebs solution, which is provided by aeration with gas containing O₂ (95%) and SO₂ (5%)

Pt-electrodes were carried out using the papillary muscle drug contraction activity studied under isometric conditions, 60 min before the start of the experiment. in order for stable contraction activity and electrogenesis to occur in the muscle during, incubation was carried out using a current with a frequency of 0.1 Hz (at a duration of 5 MS). After incubation, the maximum isometric contraction length of the papillary muscle (L_{max}) was found, and all experiments were carried out under these conditions. With the help of the capillary muscle drug ESL-2 electrostimulator (Russia), the Bore was triggered by Pt-electrodes with a current force directed at an angle, its mechanical activity was transmitted through the ft30 mechanotron to the Tam-a (Germany) amplifier and recorded on a special paper through the line Recorder TZ 4620 (Czechoslovakia) samopise.

When performing the work, *Aconitum zeravshanicum* was isolated from the plant species, the

alkaloids of the diterpene series – 15-acetoxiazometin atizin (4v-methyl-15v 15 - acetoxyatiz 16,17-en-N, 20-imin) and 15-hydroxyazometin atizin (4v

Results obtained and their analysis.

In the experiments we initially carried out, the alkaloid 15-gaa attenuated the force of the capillary muscle contraction to a maximum of $92.7 \pm 2.4\%$ compared to the control at a concentration of $30 \mu\text{m}$ at a frequency of 0.5 Hz, and its concentration of half the maximum impact on the activity of the capillary muscle contraction was $ED_{50} = 8.7 \pm 2.7 \mu\text{m}$. It was also found in our experiments that 15-aaa alkaloid rat heart papillary muscle has a dose-dependent effect on contraction activity i.e. positive inotrop effect on the force of capillary muscle contraction at lower concentration ($3-8 \mu\text{m}$) and low excitation frequencies ($< 1 \text{ Hz}$), high concentration ($10-30 \mu\text{m}$) and high excitation frequencies ($> 1 \text{ Hz}$) have a negative inotropic effect In order to substantiate the positive and negative inotropic effect effects of these studied alkloids, we found that in muxit the SA2+-channel specific blocker – nifedipine, the NA+- channel blocker – lidocaine and the NA+/Ca2+- effect on the exchange system is its blocker – In the medium $5 \mu\text{m}$ nifedipine in the existing conditions, when we

observed the effect of $15\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ concentration of 30-gaa alkaloid on the activity of capillary muscle contraction, we additionally reduced the contraction force by $19.5 \pm 4.3\%$ (Figure 1 a). Also, in experiments, when we observed the effect of the concentration of $15 \mu\text{m}$ of the alkaloid 15-aaa in the conditions of the activity of the capillary muscle contraction in conditions where the concentration of the semi-maximum action of nifedipine in the environment is $5 \mu\text{m}$, the capillary muscle contraction force nifedipine reduced by an additional $37.6 \pm 6.3\%$ compared to

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Figure 1. Rat heart papillary muscle contraction force of alkaloids 15-gaa and 15-aaa effect of nifedipine in the medium under existing conditions. On the ordinate axis-the force of contraction of the papillary muscle, expressed as a percentage in relation to control, was taken as 100%. The frequency of excitation of the drug is 0.5 Hz. In all cases, $p < 0.05$, ($n=4$).

From the results of this study, we can conclude that a lower decrease in the activity of papillary muscle contraction under the influence of 15-gaa in the presence of nifedipine indicates that its negative inotropic effect is mainly associated with Ca^{2+} -channels. Due to the presence of the hydroxyl group in the carbon atom S-15 in the 15-gaa molecule, it apparently manifests its selective interaction with Ca^{2+} - channels. Selective blocking of 15-gaa Ca^{2+} - channels effectively reduces the entry of orcali Ca^{2+} ions into cardiomyocytes, since it determines the force of contraction of the heart muscles, and the negative inotropic effect is manifested in the yakkolrok. In the medium Ca^{2+} - channels blocker nifedipine under the existing conditions, the strength of the

negative inotropic effect of the alkaloid 15-aaa, which indicates that its negative inotropic effect is low alocadence with the blockade of these channels.

As a continuation of our above experiments, the negative inotropic effect of the 15-gaa alkaloid on the activity of the capillary muscle contraction of the rat heart may be associated with the effect on the activity of cardiomyocyte na^{+} -channel. We checked this estimate using the NA^{+} - channel blocker-lidocaine. In experiments, it was found that lidocaine has a negative inotropic effect on the activity of capillary muscle contraction depending on the dose, with a minimum effect at a frequency of excitation of 0.5 Hz starting from $5 \mu m$ and reducing the amplitude of contraction force at a concentration of $30 \mu m$ to a maximum of $90.0 \pm 4.8\%$ compared to In this case, the concentration of half the maximum effect of lidocaine on the activity of capillary muscle contraction (ED_{50}) = $15 \pm 3.4 \mu m$. In experiments, it was found that under the influence of the concentration of lidocaine $15 \mu m$, the force of capillary muscle contraction decreases by $50.0 \pm 4.3\%$. Under these conditions, when we observed the effect of the alkaloid 15-gaa on the activity of capillary muscle contraction, the contraction force

lidocaine reduced by an additional 35.4±5.7% compared to the existing conditions (Figure 2 a). During our experiments, lidocaine reduced the capillary muscle contraction force to an additional 20.4±5.9% compared to the existing conditions of lidocaine when we exposed 15-aaa alkaloid to 30-µm concentrations in the environment at 15 µm available conditions (Figure 2 b).

Figure 2. The effect of alkaloids 15-gaa and 15-aaa on the activity of capillary muscle contraction in conditions where lidocaine is present in the environment. On the ordinate axis-the force of contraction of the papillary muscle, expressed as a percentage in relation to control, was taken as 100%. The frequency of excitation of the drug is 0.5 Hz. In all cases, $p < 0.05$, (n=4-5).

Based on the analysis of the results of this experiment, the effect of alkaloids in the conditions of partial blocking of NA⁺-channels is significantly reduced, this condition

can be explained by a decrease in the number of open channels interacting with alkaloids. The relatively low sensitivity of the Na⁺-channels to blocking 15 indicates that its negative inotropic effect is to a lesser extent dependent on blocking the NA⁺-channels and is mainly provided by an additional mechanism aimed at reducing the force of muscle contraction. Under the conditions of partial blocking of Na⁺-channels of the 15th

aaa alkaloid, the effect is much less likely, this condition can be explained by a decrease in the number of open channels interacting with the alkaloid. At the same time, the decrease in the negative inotropic effect of 15-AAA under the conditions of blocking of NA⁺-channels indicates that its negative inotropic effect is more focused on blocking Na⁺-channels.

15-decrease in the force of contraction of the papillary muscle under the action of the alkaloid gaa Na⁺ / Ca²⁺ - exchange system Sa²⁺ transportig In the experiment, it was found that when we observed the effect of KB-R7943 on the force of capillary muscle contraction, we reduced the dose-dependent effect

by a maximum of $24.8 \pm 3.9\%$ compared to the control of muscle contraction force at a concentration of $30 \mu\text{m}$. Under these conditions, the semi-maximum impact concentration of KB-R7943 was $ED_{50} = 20.6 \pm 3.1 \mu\text{m}$, reducing the force of capillary muscle contraction by $50.0 \pm 4.5\%$ compared to control. In the environment KB-R7943 was found to reduce the concentration of $20.6 \mu\text{m}$ of 15 to $30 \mu\text{m}$ under existing conditions by an additional $23.4 \pm 3.3\%$ compared to the effect of KB-R7943 when we observed the effect on the activity of capillary muscle contraction (Figure 3 A). We can assume that the effect of this alkaloid on the activity of capillary muscle contraction in the existing conditions KB-R7943 is significantly reduced compared to $92.7 \pm 2.4\%$ in the control variant. We can explain this condition by the effect of the alkaloid on reducing the entry of Ca^{2+} ions into the cell through the $\text{Na}^{+}/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ -exchange system. Also in the environment there is a concentration of $20.6 \mu\text{m}$ of KB-R7943 sh

Figure 3. Effect of alkaloids 15-gaa and 15-aaa on the activity of capillary muscle contraction $\text{Na}^{+}/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ - exchange system blocker-KB-R7943 in existing conditions. On the ordinate axis-the force of contraction of the papillary muscle, expressed as a percentage in relation to control, was taken as 100%. The frequency of excitation of the drug is 0.5 Hz. In all cases, $p < 0.05$ ($n = 4-5$).

In order to add to the above points and clarify further, the experiment used cardiac glycoside-ouabain in the study of the role of the $\text{Na}^{+}/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ - exchange system in the effect of the 15 - aaa alkaloid on the

activity of capillary muscle contraction. In our above experiments, it was observed that when we observed the effect of ouabain on the activity of papillary muscle contraction, it had a positive inotropic effect depending on the dose, increasing the contraction force at a concentration of 20 μm by $84.8 \pm 5.3\%$ compared to control (100% obtained). Also in this experiment, its blocker-nifedipine - was used in order to eliminate the entry of the Ca^{2+} ion through the potential-dependent Ca^{2+} channel. In the experiment, the concentration of nifedipine 10 μm increased the force of capillary muscle contraction by $68.6 \pm 3.6\%$ when we affected the concentration of ouabainning 20 μm under existing conditions. The contraction called ouabain in this case is only due to Ca^{2+} ions entering through the $\text{Na}^{+}/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ -exchange system. Under these conditions, the half-maximum k of 15 In the experiment, it was found that 15-AAA also has a negative inotropic effect depending on the dose in relation to the force of the capillary muscle contraction, which is called using ouabain. The semi-maximum concentration of 15-AAA (ED50) under the influence of 16.7 μm , the force of capillary muscle contraction, called using ouabain, decreased from $68.6 \pm 3.6\%$ to $34.7 \pm 5.1\%$ and the maximum

concentration decreased to $15.4 \pm 3.8\%$ under the influence of 30 μm (Figure 4 B).

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Figure 4. The effect of

alkaloids 15-gaa and 15-aaa on the force of capillary muscle contraction, called using ouabain.

On the ordinate axis-the force of contraction of the papillary muscle, expressed as a percentage in relation to control, was taken as 100%. The frequency of excitation of the drug is 0.5 Hz. In all cases, $p < 0.05$ ($n = 4-5$).

Based on the analysis of the results obtained, we can trace the decrease in the force of capillary muscle contraction, called by ouabain under the influence of 15-gaa and 15-aaa, with the effect of the reduction of the penetration of Ca^{2+} ions into the cell through the Na^{+}/Ca^{2+} -exchange system under the influence of these alkaloids.

Conclusions

The negative inotropic effect of 15-gaa and 15-AAA is mainly associated with the blockade of the Na^{+} -channels, which is determined

to occur together with modifications of the function of Ca^{2+} - carrier systems that lead to a decrease in the level of Ca^{2+} ions in cardiomyocytes.

An important role in ensuring the negative inotropic effect of alkaloids 15-gaa and 15-aaa was played by the Na^{+}/Ca^{2+} -exchange system, the activation of which in conditions of a blockade of neither Ca^{2+} - channels and a decrease in the amount of Na^{+} ions was determined by an increase in the outflow of Ca^{2+} ions from cardiomyocytes.

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